

INFLUENCE OF LASER RADIATION ON METAL MELTING AND FORMATION OF SEAMS IN ARC WELDING (REVIEW)

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ABSTRACT

Research articles devoted to the development of laser-plasma processes in the last two decades are considered. It has been established that modern directions of scientific research of laser-plasma welding processes are mainly aimed at studying the features of the joint action on steel and alloys of compressed arc plasma and laser radiation with a wavelength of 1.03-1.07 microns (primarily fiber laser), and as well as studying the physical foundations of the manifestation of the synergistic (hybrid) effect in such an action and determining the possibilities of its practical application. In particular, it was determined that the increase in the effectiveness of the manifestation of the synergistic effect is associated with the improvement of the burning conditions of the plasma arc in the zone of the ionized vapor torch, which is formed under the action of focused laser radiation, as well as the simplification of the formation of the laser keyhole due to the pressure of the plasma arc.

Keywords: arc welding, laser-plasma welding, synergistic effect, process efficiency, steels, aluminum alloys.

The joining of steel sheets and aluminum alloys is becoming more and more important in modern production. Traditional arc welding methods create a thermally affected zone (HAZ) of considerable size, which is characterized by reduced mechanical characteristics and, first of all, strength [1]. The issue of HAZ minimization is especially important for welding aluminum alloys [2]. One of the ways to eliminate this shortcoming is the use of highly concentrated sources of energy, such as laser radiation. The combination of laser radiation with arc welding sources allows not only to reduce the size of the HAZ, but also to increase the technological parameters of welding [3].

At the beginning of the 21st century Acad. I.V. Krivtsun claimed [4-6] that the main factors determining the nature of metal penetration during combined laser-arc welding are the thermal and dynamic effects of the used heat sources on the surface of the welding bath. Therefore, he developed a system of equations to describe the process of metal vaporization under the action of a multicomponent plasma formed above the welding bath during laser-plasma welding [7]. Such a system forms the basis for calculating the characteristics of thermal and dynamic effects of arc, laser or combined plasma on the surface of the welding bath for the appropriate methods of welding in shielding gases. In the next step, he investigated the peculiarities of metal penetration during laser-arc welding using the

Nd:YAG-laser [8]. The developed mathematical model of thermal processes during laser-arc welding using an Nd:YAG-laser and an argon arc made it possible to calculate the penetration profiles under the combined effect of a laser beam and an electric arc on the product, taking into account their interaction on the metal surface. The calculations showed the presence of a synergistic (hybrid) effect, which is contained in a non-additive increase in the volume of metal remelted by the laser-plasma method, compared to the volumes of metal remelted separately by laser and plasma methods.

In order to analyse the effect of synergistic coupling that occurs during the process, laser-plasma welding can be divided into three zones [9]: (I) plasma above the surface, (II) the surface of the weld pool, and (III) the occurrence of interaction directly below the surface. Factors such as the common welding source, the mutual location of the laser and plasma sources, as well as the role and influence of the welding parameters, exert the main influence on the degree of manifestation of the synergistic effect.

In work [10], it was shown that the characteristics of the arc practically do not change in the cases of interaction "gas CO₂-laser – helium TIG arc" and "disc Yb:YAG-laser – argon TIG arc". The reason is that the inverse bremsstrahlung absorption coefficients are very different due to the different electron densities of argon and helium arcs and the different wavelengths of CO₂

and Yb:YAG-lasers. Such a study in a certain way contributes to the partial application of the experience of using a CO₂-laser in hybrid processes with radiation from solid-state lasers.

The work [11] presents the results of the study of the synergistic effect of hybrid laser-arc welding. The experiments were performed with a Nd:YAG-laser with a power of $P_L=500$ W in combination with standard equipment for TIG welding. Two aspects were investigated: heat transfer efficiency and melting efficiency. The efficiency of heat transfer was determined by calorimetric measurements, and the efficiency of melting was determined by the cross-sections of welds obtained at different welding modes. The results show that the interaction of the laser and the arc does not lead to a noticeable change in the heat transfer efficiency, but leads to a significant increase in the melting efficiency. The non-additive increase in the cross-sectional area of the seams obtained by the addition of two heat sources (laser and arc) indicates the presence of a synergistic effect and the hybrid nature of welding.

Spectral analysis of the hybrid plasma torch and high-speed photographic analysis of the process come to the rescue when investigating the manifestation of the synergistic effect in hybrid welding [12]. The following is established. Firstly, the principle of the synergy effect is that when interacting with a compressed arc of a non-melting electrode, the laser transfers the

electron energy to a higher level and creates the conditions for a quantum transition. Thanks to this, more photons are emitted, which increase the flow of heat to the welded material. The synergistic effect is quantified by the spectral intensity. It increases with increasing laser power and decreases with arc current. This effect is proportional to the cross-section of the weld, especially its upper part. Secondly, the number of spatters in hybrid laser-arc welding is much smaller than in arc welding.

In work [13], a number of studies of laser-plasma welding according to the scheme of Fig.1 were carried out. It is proposed to determine the welding efficiency η_w as the ratio of the theoretical value of the P_{FZ} power required to melt the material of the melting zone (FZ index) to the total supplied welding power P_w according to

$$\eta_w = \frac{P_{FZ}}{P_w} = \frac{\rho \cdot w_{ch} \cdot A_{FZ} \cdot \Delta h_{FZ}}{P_w} \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the mass density of the material to be welded, w_{ch} is the speed of movement, A_{FZ} is the cross-sectional area of the melting zone, and Δh_{FZ} is the required increase in the specific enthalpy for melting. Ratio (1) can be considered as a basis for determining relative welding efficiency, which compares the efficiency of the combined laser-plasma process with the efficiency of individual processes. In this case, we get:

Fig. 1. Experimental setup with a separate location of the plasmatorn and laser beam [13]: 1 – plasma burner located at an angle $\alpha=35^\circ$ (backward angle); 2 – plasma nozzle (distance to the sample $L=2$ mm); 3 – laser beam directed at an angle $\beta=20^\circ$ (forward angle); 4 – cross-jet (air knife); 5 – high-speed camera; 6 – protective glass; 7 – sample; 8 – the direction of movement of the desktop (sample).

$$\eta_{rel} = \frac{\eta_{PL}}{\eta_{P+L}} = \frac{\rho \cdot A_{FZ,PL} \cdot \Delta h_{FZ} \cdot w_{ch}}{P_p + P_L} \cdot \frac{P_p + P_L}{\rho \cdot (A_{FZ,P} + A_{FZ,L}) \cdot \Delta h_{FZ} \cdot w_{ch}} = \frac{A_{FZ,PL}}{A_{FZ,P} + A_{FZ,L}} \quad (2)$$

In this regard, $A_{FZ,PL}$ denotes the cross-sectional area of the seam of the combined laser-plasma process, and $A_{FZ,P}$ and $A_{FZ,L}$ are the cross-sectional area of the seams made separately by plasma and laser welding.

Calculated values of measured weld cross-sectional areas and corresponding relative efficiencies are shown in Table 1 for ASTM A284 medium carbon steel, AISI 304 stainless steel, and 6082 aluminum alloy.

Table 1.

Cross-sectional areas of the A_{FZ} welding seam and the resulting relative efficiency η_w of plasma, laser and laser-plasma welding of plates ($P_L=600$ W, $I_P=100$ A) [13].

No	Material	Thickness δ , mm	Welding speed V , m/min	$A_{FZ,P}$ / mm ²	$A_{FZ,L}$ / mm ²	$A_{FZ,PL}$ / mm ²	η_w / -
(1)	ASTM A284	10,0	0,5	0,4	1,5	3,3	1,74
(2)	AISI 304	1,5	1,5	0,1	0,7	1,9	2,38
(3)	6082	2,5	1,5	2,2	1,8	6,0	1,50

One of the reasons for increasing the efficiency of laser-plasma welding compared to individual processes can be a change in the arc voltage when laser radiation is introduced into the plasma-arc process. In particular, characteristic differences in arc voltage during welding of steels and aluminum alloys were revealed. In the case of aluminum welding, there is a noticeable drop in the arc voltage in the range of -2 to -3 V when the laser beam is turned on, while when welding steel under the same conditions of a highly focused laser beam, a moderate increase in the arc voltage between 0.15 and 0.6 V was found.

If the synergistic effect of hybrid laser-arc processing is explained as an increase in energy transfer from heat sources to the material, the thermal efficiency or overall efficiency of the process η_T corresponds to the ratio of the P_U power required to melt the welded material per unit time (without losses) to the total applied power P_A [14]. This value can be divided according to equation (3) into the melting efficiency η_M (use of energy inside the base material) and the efficiency of energy coupling η_C (energy input from heat sources) using the power P_T , which is transferred from the heat sources to the workpiece [14]:

$$\eta_T = \frac{P_U}{P_A} = \eta_M \times \eta_C = \frac{P_U}{P_T} \times \frac{P_T}{P_A} \quad (3)$$

Taking into account the heat flow entering the welded workpiece and the energy coupling efficiency η_C depending on it, the estimated weld cross-sections in combination with equation (4) [14] are used to determine the thermal efficiency η_T :

$$\eta_T = \frac{P_U}{P_A} = \frac{v_x \cdot A_S \cdot \rho \cdot (c_p \cdot (\vartheta_s - \vartheta_\infty) + h_s)}{U_{Arc} \cdot I_{Arc} + P_L} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 2. Cross-sections of welding of AISI304 steel ($\delta=1$ mm) with a laser beam ($P_L = 200$ W; $\omega_0 = 200$ μ m), plasma welding ($Q_P = 1.8$ l/min; $d_w = 5$ mm) and laser-plasma welding (LaPAW) ($P_L = 200$ W; $\omega_0 = 200$ μ m; $Q_P = 1.8$ l/min; $d_w = 5$ mm) with corresponding efficiency values [15].

where v_x — welding speed, A_S — weld area, probe density, c_p — specific heat capacity, ϑ_s i ϑ_∞ — melting point and ambient temperature, h_s — enthalpy of fusion, P_L — laser power, U_{Arc} and I_{Arc} — arc voltage and current respectively. Then the melting efficiency η_M is the result of applying equation (3).

The method and model of efficiency determination were applied in the work [15]. While a laser beam with a power of $P_L=200$ W and a focus point diameter of 200 μ m barely melts the material, the plasma welding process with an arc power of about 2 kW achieves the penetration of the weld by approximately 2/3 of the thickness of the workpiece for the applied set of parameters (Fig.2). The combination of both processes gives welding with complete penetration. While the η_C energy coupling efficiency is only modestly increased by about 10% compared to the arithmetic η_C energy coupling efficiency of the individual processes, the η_M melting efficiency of the combined process is about 1.5 times higher than the η_M melting efficiency of the plasma-arc process. It can be hypothesized that the heat flow within the weld pool, driven by conductive and/or convective transfer mechanisms, is advantageously altered to create a resulting weld cross-section with increased penetration due to more favorable thermal and/or hydrodynamic boundary conditions. The authors of the work [15] propose to consider this as a clear proof of the hypothesis that secondary, i.e. thermal, effects are responsible for the synergistic benefits of the productivity of laser-arc processing.

The work [16] confirmed the presence of a synergistic effect in laser-plasma welding using a fiber laser by comparing the cross-sectional areas of welds made in an AISI 304 plate ($\delta=4$ mm) by laser, plasma, and hybrid methods at close values of the power of laser radiation and plasma arcs (~ 2 kW each). It was determined that the manifestation of this effect depends on the welding speed. At a speed of 2 m/min, the cross-sectional area of hybrid welding exceeds the sum of the planes obtained by laser and plasma methods by 30%, and at a speed of 4 m/min – $\sim 20\%$.

In work [17], the dimensionless parameter of the increase in melting energy ψ ($\psi = \frac{S_H - (S_L + S_A)}{S_L + S_A} * 100\%$, was used to quantify the synergistic effect in laser-arc

hybrid welding, where S_H , S_L , S_A – cross-sectional area of hybrid, laser and arc welding seams, respectively). The greater the value of ψ , the stronger the synergistic effect. ψ was calculated and compared at different parameters of laser-TIG and laser-MIG hybrid welding. The first had a stronger synergistic effect ($\psi=59.3-83.6\%$) than the second ($\psi=1-23\%$). It can be expected that in the case of using arc plasma (i.e. compressed electric arc) in the hybrid process, the synergistic effect will be even greater than in laser-TIG welding [18]. This effect can be estimated for laser-plasma welding using the Nd:YAG laser by grinding the cross-sections shown in Fig.3 and 4, respectively, of the specified mode parameters.

Fig. 3. Formation of a weld in S235JR steel sheets with a thickness of 3 mm caused by a change in the power of laser radiation (a) 0 W; (b) 220 W; (c) 330 W; (d) 440 W (constant parameters: $I = 150$ A; $V = 1000$ mm/min; $Q_P = 0.8$ l/min, $L = 8$ mm, $\beta = 3^\circ$) [18].

Fig. 4. Formation of a weld on S235JR steel sheets with a thickness of 4 mm due to a change in the power of laser radiation (a) 0 W; (b) 440 W; (c) 0 W; (d) 440 W and welding speed: a), b) 200 mm/min, c), d) 250 mm/min (unchanged parameters: $I = 150$ A; $Q_P = 0.4$ l/min, $L = 8$ mm, $\beta = 19^\circ$) [18].

To implement the processes of laser-plasma welding, the focused laser beam can be directed to the point of interaction with the material at a certain angle, i.e. according to the paraxial scheme (Fig.1) (for example, [19]) or perpendicular to the surface of the product being welded, i.e. according to the coaxial scheme (for example, [6, 20]). Structurally, the laser-plasma welding head can consist of separate elements – a laser focusing system and a plasmatron, or be integrated into a general body. The plasma torch is usually tilted at a certain (minimum possible) angle to the axis of the focused

laser beam [21]. The bonding wire can be fed towards the plasma jet or not fed at all. Also, powders of metals and alloys can be used as filler materials [22, 23]. In the case of using powder filler materials, important technological parameters of welding are the distance between the processed workpiece and the laser-plasma head, as well as the arc current [23]. The influence of the arc current mainly ensures the formation of the upper roller, while the power of the laser radiation ensures the formation of the penetration depth (Fig.5).

Fig. 5. The ratio between the cross-sectional area of the weld metal obtained by the plasma powder process and the area obtained by the laser process, depending on the plasma arc current for two different welding speeds [23].

The analysis of literary data allows us to formulate the following main advantages of the hybrid laser-plasma process in comparison with plasma-arc and laser:

- the joint use of laser and plasma energy allows to reduce the laser power and reduce the cost of the equipment (estimated up to 40-50%);
- the laser component of laser-plasma welding allows to reduce the size of the HAZ;
- the plasma component of laser-plasma welding allows to reduce requirements for preparation and assembly of welded edges;
- increase in productivity due to increase in welding speed;
- reduction of energy consumption due to improvement of process efficiency;
- expansion of the deposited roller during laser-plasma deposition and increase of penetration depth during welding due to changes in hydrodynamic currents in the welding bath.

Conclusions.

1. The study of literary sources showed that modern directions of scientific research of laser-plasma welding processes are mainly aimed at studying the features of the joint action on steels and alloys of compressed arc plasma and laser radiation with a wavelength of 1.03-1.07 microns (primarily - fiber laser), as well as on the study of the physical foundations of the manifestation of the synergistic (hybrid) effect in such an action and the determination of the possibilities of its practical application.

2. It was determined that the promotion of the manifestation of the synergistic effect is connected with

the improvement of the burning conditions of the plasma arc in the zone of the ionized vapor torch formed under the action of focused laser radiation, as well as the simplification of the formation of the laser keyhole due to the pressure of the plasma arc.

3. The effectiveness of the manifestation of the synergistic effect during laser-plasma welding of steels and alloys is proposed to be determined as the ratio of the theoretical amount of power required to melt the weld material to the total supplied welding power, or as the ratio of the cross-sectional area of the laser-plasma weld to the sum of the cross-sectional areas seams made separately by plasma and laser welding. It was established that the efficiency of laser-plasma welding can vary from 1.5 (for aluminum alloy 6082) to 2.4 (for AISI304 steel).

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